

In Children Interest in Reading Books Formation Features

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Abstract:

In this article, people influencing the manifestation of interest in reading in schoolchildren, instilling a love of books in children, choosing the right place to read books, helping more adults in the process of reading books, analyzing the work done. the.

Keywords: reader, child, book, reading, family, parents, motivation, cooperation, freedom of choice, fear, conformity, involvement.

Introduction.

Your child education, upbringing and in development book he plays big floor. Students book with at work reasonable methods with without arming successful education to give possible it's not. Because knowledge, skill and skills take over, not only teacher using done is increased, perhaps independent respectively different artistic sources reading learning, role games and to the cocktail orientation done in the process increased _

Studying the psychological characteristics of children's interest in reading books is one of the most urgent issues. In particular, it is important to determine how students' interest in reading outside the school program can affect the child's personality. It is known that in the world psychological practice, we can see that people who read books for the blind increase their outlook, thinking, and creativity, and it is also proven that the motivation of children who read books is better.

Even though reading occupies the main place in the activities of elementary school students, like play and work, the organization of this process did not happen by itself. Effective and successful organization of the reading process in primary classes is ensured not only by the formation of students' reading skills, but also by the existence of appropriate pedagogical and psychological conditions for their development, taking into account their individual characteristics. The article

talks about the redagogical-psychological context of the formation of reading skills in elementary school students.

Analysis of literature on the subject

The concept of "Mutolaa" ("reading a book") means "read carefully", "study" when translated from Arabic. Theoretically, this concept means "careful reading", "reading and understanding" [2; p. 416]. It should not be forgotten that reading books is hard work for elementary school students. The main content of the school student's education is the transition from one level of knowledge to another, from one level of acquisition of cognitive and practical skills to another, step by step to a higher level. He learns only when he is interested, willingly" [1]. According to V.A. Sukhomlinskiu, "reading a book is like a path for an intelligent, thinking educator to encourage a child's heart" [3; p. 287]. Hitting the trail was not always easy. Therefore, it is advisable to organize this process gradually, but consistently. V.A. Sukhomlinskiu, speaking about the importance of book teaching, says the following: "books play a big role in children's morale, only when the child can read well." What is meant by "good reading"? This is, first of all, mastering the simplest skill - reading technique.

Analysis and results

In order to study the psychological characteristics of children's interest in reading books during our research, we used the author's questionnaire "Determining the activity of reading books in the child's free time".

As the object of our research, 146 elementary school students, 134 junior high school students, total of 280 respondent students of schools of Tashkent city and Urganch city and Urganch district were selected. We conducted our research in three stages.

In the 1st stage, the levels of interest in reading books of primary and pre-adolescent students, we used the methods given below.

In the 2nd stage, we divided "beginner" and "average students" into experimental groups, and "book lovers" and "real readers" into control groups. In order to create an interest in reading, we conducted training sessions of the development program called "A good friend from a book".

At the 3rd stage, the methodology of "Formula of interest in reading a book" was tested in experimental and control group subjects in the retest method, and the effectiveness of the developed development program was proven, based on which we developed conclusions and recommendations.

From the very first days of education, various contradictions, contradictions, and internal conflicts, which drive the development of children in junior high school, begin to arise. At the root of these are the level of psychological maturity of the child and the contradictions between positive qualities and requirements. The increase in demands requires the continuous development of the child psychologically, and as a result of continuous movement as a chain of this development, human maturity is realized. Pupils' interest in the content of education and their knowledge acquisition is closely related to the feeling of satisfaction from the results of one's intellectual work. Children's sense of pride, self-confidence, acquisition of knowledge and strengthening of skills are developed through book characters.

As we have seen above, children are interested in books from early childhood. According to observations, at first he is interested in turning pages, listening to adult reading, looking at pictures. As soon as the interest in the picture grew, the interest in the text began to grow. Research shows that the child's interest in the fate of the hero of the story can be aroused by the third child, and the child can follow the development of events and experience his feelings about him. As we mentioned above, one of the characteristics of children's perception of literary works is sympathy for

characters. The process of perception takes an active part in this, the child puts himself in the place of the hero, fights against enemies with his creativity through mental actions. E.A. Flerina said that the children did not have a bad time, the hero should be lucky (the children did not want even the stupid mouse to be eaten by the cat).

In order to study the problem of the interest of children and teenagers in reading literature and literature, we co-authored with our head of science "Determining the activity of reading books in the free time of children" We were satisfied with the questionnaire.

Ask the children: "What kind of books do you like to read?" was asked and the results are summarized in Table 1 below.

43.36% of children decided to read books with electronic version, while 56.64% gave priority to books with paper version. Most of the children in the oral question-answer process chose e-books, the convenience of taking them with them, and the fact that they can quickly find the necessary information, but in the process of marking the questionnaire, they chose books with a paper version.

Types of children's books (n=280)

What kind of books do you like to read?	%
Electronic version books	43.36%
Paper version books	56.64%
Total	100 % _

From these answers, all children enjoy reading, and we know that reading is a key activity for students in elementary school. Children like books with better paper versions.

We were also interested in children's reading intensity, how long they read a book.

Children's opinions about the intensity of reading books (%) (n=280)

2. I book read _ _	%
a) each 1 in oud	23, 0 6
b) each 1 in the village	23.61
c) 1 boy 2 _	25
g) 1 6 in the village ta	16.67
d)	11.6 6
Total	100 % _

Keuing to the question: How many books do I read? write your answer instead of the dots and choose one of the answers, if you don't have an answer that suits you, write the answer that suits you instead of the dots, the question was read to the students, the students chose the answers that fit them , if the answer did not match, they left the appropriate answer instead of dots. We can see the result in the table above.

As can be seen in the above table, 25% of children read two books in one house, 23.61% children read one book in each house, and 23.06% children read one book in each house. 16.67% of children read 6 books at home, and 16.67% of children read 4 books at home. Thus, it was found that a quarter of the children we surveyed read one book per class.

The third question in our questionnaire " What kind of books do I like?" the question was thoroughly answered.

Children's opinions about reading books of various genres.

To this question, the children answered " fairy tale book". From Figure 2.1, we can see that 37% of

elementary school students like to read fairy tales, 26% like to read adventure books, and 19% of students like to read romance books. chose 6% of children answered that they read books according to their preferences. Because the main activity of elementary school students is reading, acquiring knowledge, thinking, speech, attention, behavior, and memory are formed through reading. they delay reading books, because children want fairy tales to end with good things. Elementary school students begin to understand themselves and think about what is good and what is bad , and show it to the people around them through their actions. An additional question was asked during the survey process. " Can you do anything without a book?" to the question, the blind children answered that they could not, and the reason was explained with difficulty. The most common answer was " I don't know". It was found during the research that children love to read fairy tales and adventure books. The fourth question of the questionnaire was about whether children read books from the cover.

The next question in the questionnaire was about how children spend their free time. « In my free time, I am more blind?» the question was asked and the following answers were received.

Opinions of children about how they spend their free time (n=280)

In my free time, I am more blind ...	%
a) TV set i see	28.89
b) with my friend _ _ _ I'm confused	29.44
c) book reading i do	28
d) Ijtimoi u t a rmoqd a o tir a m a n _	10.61
d)	3, 0 6
Total	100 % _

In the table above, children who are blind are the most blind in their free time - 29.44% answered that I hang out with my friend. As we know, quarreling with a close friend, communication was a leading activity during adolescence. Given that most of the test takers are teenagers, the answers are self-explanatory. 28.89% of children answered that they watch TV, and 28% of children answered that they read books. 10.61% of children reported that they sit on the phone on social networks and play various games. 3.06% of children reported that they take care of their work and take care of their siblings. So, it can be concluded from the answers that one third of the children who took part in the survey spend their free time in front of the TV while arguing with their friends in their free time. Only one-fifth of respondents reported that they read books in their free time.

The sixth question in the questionnaire: "Do your family members often read to you?" and the following answers were obtained from the students, the obtained information is summarized in Table 5.

Family members reading books to their children (n=280)

Answer options	%
very rarely	47.2%
when they have free time	52.8%
Total	100 % _

47.2% of children answered "very rarely", 52.8% answered "when family members (parents, siblings, grandparents) have free time". they answered. It was found that more than half of the children who took part in the survey read books to family members only when they have free time. As children get older, family members rarely ask them to read books. It should be noted that one of the factors that increase the child's love for books and interest in reading is that the older members of the family spend more time with the child and read books.

Figure 2. Helping family members read books to children.

The seventh question in the survey was also interesting for us, the information about who encourages children to read books, the results are shown in the picture below.

It was found that 47% of grandparents, 22% of siblings, and 31% of parents take the lead in reading books to children. It has been proven that children's interest in reading books begins with their family, grandparents, parents, siblings, which allows us to understand that it is a situation related to our values.

Thus, a survey conducted with elementary school students and teenagers revealed that all children are encouraged by family members to read to children in their free time, and blind grandparents they learn to read books, they like fairy-tale books.

Summary

Children's reading should consist of works of various genres: stories, novels, fairy tales, poems, lyrical and humorous poems, short stories, etc. This, on the one hand, makes it possible to form a wide range of interest in reading books. On the other hand, it is worth highlighting the role of the cultural layer, which is a repository of folk wisdom, traditions, morals and morals, as well as selection of literary advantages, individuality, folk epics, legends, folklore. Classical literature is also the bearer of folk culture. They solve the most complex issues of morality, values, morality and choice in a convenient way.

Figure 3. Demonstration of interest in reading in primary school students.

Conclusion: Based on the results of this research, it is appropriate to state the following conclusions:

1. Children prefer paper versions of books to more visually appealing e-books. Only a quarter of children read one book every day.
2. Children love to read fairy tales and adventure books.
3. Children read badiyu books from blind libraries.
4. The majority of children watch TV in their free time, argue with their friends, only one fifth of respondents read books in their free time.
5. Family members read books to their children when adults have free time.
6. Blind grandparents are active in reading to children.
7. A third of primary school students who participated in the study are real readers and book lovers.

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